

California Wildfire Ignition Causes from 1980 to 2019

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ABSTRACT

Natural climate variability, fire suppression management, human ignition, and vegetation can all contribute to the behavior of wildfires. As fires increase in frequency and intensity, it is becoming increasingly crucial that ignition causes are studied and considered when planning fire suppression and prevention strategies, recovery management, and fire safety education. This study focuses on California, where, like much of western United States, fire activity and incidences are most prominent. From the CALFIRE database and Redbooks, we leverage data on fire-ignition causes from 1980 to 2019 on CALFIRE-protected lands and analyze ignitions patterns and distributions across California. On average, the number of wildfire disasters have steadily increased throughout this period. 16 distinct causes were identified, the three most commonly occurring being lightning, electrical power, and equipment use. Human-caused fires have historically dominated the record, though specific causes such as arson have shown a marked decline in recent years. Vehicular, railroad, and powerline-induced fires- amongst others- were unreported until later years, when their widespread use and integration into the modern-world would, as expected, affect ignition patterns. From 2000-2019, wildfires in northern California were primarily due to lightning and electrical power, while incidents in southern California stemmed largely from equipment use. Lightning-caused wildfires during this 40-year period showed the most significant change in frequency, as did causes recorded as ‘undetermined’ and ‘under investigation.’ Such changes in fire activity and ignition causes reflect long-term fire trends and provide important insight into how to better prevent, prepare, and act during and after wildfire disasters.

INTRODUCTION

The western United States experiences the majority of the nation's wildfire burning, historically logging some of the worst wildfires in recent decades. With a naturally changing climate, increased human participation in disaster-inducing events and activities, and anthropogenic climate change, wildfires are anticipated to grow in size, frequency, and strength over time. California is one of the most fire-prone states in the country, leading with not only the most fire events and total acreage burned, but also subsequent damage and 'deadliness' to individuals, communities, and the environment. From 1978-2018, there was a cited increase of 405% in the annual burned areas in the state (Turco et al., 2023), and of California's top largest wildfires recorded, more than half occurred in the past decade, with five of the six largest occurring in just 2 months in 2020 (Masri et al., 2021). The 2020 August Complex Fire (>1 million acres) became the 'largest' and 'most destructive' fire on state record, more than doubling and quintupling the 2018 Mendocino Complex Fire (459,123 acres) and the 2017 Thomas (281,893 acres), respectively (Masri et al., 2021).

The California Department of Forestry and Fire Protection (CAL FIRE), the state's primary fire agency, highlights climate change as the driving factor contributing to wildfire events, but also records the direct cause(s) of each event, amongst other variables, in its Redbooks. The four most common ignition sources on lands under CAL FIRE jurisdiction, covering 51 of the state's 58 counties, are equipment use, powerlines, arson, and lightning (Keeley & Syphard, 2018). Human-induced fires, both accidental (such as equipment use or vehicular) and intentional (arson) have been cited as the primary source of wildfires, responsible for most of the fires reported from 1919 to 2016 and accounting for 95% or more of the ignitions in two-thirds of the counties (Keeley & Syphard, 2018). Further human encroachment into the

wilderness and the expansion of the wildlife-urban interface (WUI) as a result also heightens the risk of wildfires, because the WUI often contains large amounts of flammable vegetation, and firefighting efforts are difficult due to differences in the training and equipment between structural firefighters and wildland firefighters (Masri et al., 2023). Even fire suppression practices— a system that seeks to control or even entirely prevent fires from occurring— are also an unforeseen contributor to wildfires because they lead to a buildup of dead biomass, which serves as dangerous and flammable fuel for wildfires.

As average temperatures in California steadily rise and the world continues to battle the consequences of climate change, warmer temperatures bring about more risk of wildfire occurrences. The buildup of dry vegetation over time, periods of heavier-than-usual rainfall, extreme weather, lower fuel moisture, heat waves, strong winds, etc. allows wildfires to spread faster and more aggressively (Masri et al., 2021). One study shows that fires are frequent during summers in California, when it is characterized by low precipitation (or dry years following wet years), extreme heat, and atmospheric aridity. Coupled with climate change trends and patterns, three-quarters of California's forest-fire area that occurred during 1972–2018 was in North Coast and Sierra Nevada, where the annual burned areas increased by 630% and 618%, respectively, and the most significant increase was in forested regions, which experienced an increase of 766% (Turco et al., 2023). Additionally, the release of greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide is also an important consideration when investigating the ecological impacts of wildfires. Between 2001 and 2010, California wildfires released about 46 million tons of carbon, which accounts for about five to seven percent of all carbon emitted by the state during that decade (Gonzalez et al., 2015). Such correlations point to a strong fire-climate relationship, may it be anthropogenic or natural, and result in larger, more intense wildfires.

Prior research has found that a strong connection exists between wildfires and mental and physical health. Exposure to harmful, volatile byproducts and pollutants, such as particulate matter (the most common of which is PM_{2.5}) contained in the smoke released by fires can cause and/or exacerbate cerebrovascular, respiratory, and cardiovascular issues when inhaled. Chronic illnesses that were previously undiagnosed in impact survivors but would later be identified—sometimes even years after the disaster— can range anywhere from mild asthma to acute heart disease, alongside increased mortality and upticks in the number of hospital admissions and visits (Rappold et al., 2017). Adverse mental health impacts, such as depression, anxiety, and PTSD, have also been identified in survivors of wildfires; aside from the immediate burden of the fire itself, additional stress and fear from unemployment, homelessness, loss of social network(s), and financial instability all perpetuate the psychological impacts of wildfire events (Eisenman and Galway, 2022) (Rosenthal et al., 2021). Truly, the considerable short-term and long-term impacts of wildfire disasters on the human mind and body are becoming increasingly apparent to both the scientific community and the public.

To better design effective fire prevention and management strategies, and improve recovery and aid services to impacted communities, it is important to understand both historical and contemporary ignition patterns, especially since they are regulated by progressively more complex interactions among climate, topography, fuel, and humans. In this study, the location and cause(s) of ignition were examined for each wildfire disaster from 1980 to 2019 to identify any notable changes in wildfire activity over time. Specifically, the research questions/aims were as follows: (1) How have the number of *and* causes of wildfires in California changed since 1980? (2) Are there particular regions in California that are more susceptible to a certain cause and if so, how are they distributed throughout the state? (3) What accounts for the changes in

wildfire activity in California? (4) Which region in California (northern or southern) experienced the most wildfires, and how has it changed during this period?

METHODS

The California Department of Forestry and Fire Protection (CAL FIRE) is responsible for fire prevention, resource management, and providing wildland fire protection across more than 31 million acres of land throughout California, as well as the state's private and public forests (CAL FIRE, 2023). The organization works in both suppression and prevention capacities and offers emergency services of various kinds to 36 out of California's 58 counties and 115 local government cooperators (Keeley and Syphard, 2018). CAL FIRE also assists in a wide range of other disasters and incidents, including earthquakes, water rescues, and hazardous material spills. In the case of a wildfire event, the respective CAL FIRE unit records the incident data (i.e. acres burned, cause of ignition), which are later compiled into the California Redbooks. Redbooks are CAL FIRE's annual report on wildfires that occurred on land for which it is the state's responsibility to prevent and suppress wildfires and is financially liable. Each entry used in this study, the fire's Redbook year, ranger unit, fire name, start date, containment date, the development permit area (DPA), acres burned, vegetation type, cause, structures damages, structures destroyed, civilian fatalities, and fire fatalities are documented.

Using the 1980-1989 (N=553 entries), 1990-1999 (N=412 entries), and 2000-2019 (N=1145 entries) data frames from the CAL FIRE Redbooks, state and federal statistics were combined to determine the number of fires, the location, year, cause of ignition, and structures destroyed/damaged for each listed event. Data analyses, results, and statistical significance tests were obtained through original and reproducible codes written and run in R, the primary

statistical computing and data visualization/graphics software used in this study. Additional Redbook variables such as vegetation type, the DPA, number of civilian fatalities, number of fire fatalities, start date, and containment date were excluded to ensure that the variables across all data frames are identical and can be combined and assessed simultaneously by R.

Redbook year and cause of ignition were initially examined to identify ignition patterns and changes. To account for repetition and miscellaneous variations of the same cause, in addition to errors such as misspellings, each ignition cause had to first be standardized (i.e. 'equip use,' 'equipment,' and 'erquipment' were all edited to be categorized under 'equipment use'). 41 alternative names and/or spellings for ignition causes were simplified into 16 final causes and are as follows: arson, equipment use, miscellaneous, smoking, under investigation, powerlines, escape, campfire, debris, human, play with fire, undetermined/unidentified, vehicle, railroad, lightning, and electrical power. A stacked bar chart was computed to highlight how each cause may be changing from year to year, as well as display the relationship between individual causes and them as a whole.

In this study, we used geospatial data in two main ways. First, as proposed by Logan et al., statistics (i.e. the number of each ignition cause from 2000-2019) associated with distinct geographic boundaries (i.e. counties in California) can be leveraged to provide a broader context for the research. The combination of wildfire location information, attribute information, and temporal information gives a more complete picture of events from historical to current. Second, spatial data was also used to investigate patterns and trends, which enabled us to not only identify the frequency of each ignition cause but also when and where they were distributed throughout California during this period.

To spatially map the three most frequent causes of wildfires that occurred in California from 2000-2019, we used a spatial dataset that contained all wildfire disasters that occurred in the country during this period, including the state, latitudinal and longitudinal coordinates, and the geometry of each entry. For the purpose of this study, we excluded entries other than California wildfires from our analysis. The geometry attribute was removed from the data frame since each entry had to define a single point of origin on the map, not the closed shape or perimeter of a certain area. In doing so, each individual wildfire that occurred in a particular county was properly accounted for and allowed us to investigate the exact number of wildfires and their ignition cause in each region. To accurately plot the latitudinal and longitudinal coordinates as spatial (geometry) points, we assigned a coordinate reference system (CRS) and a geographic coordinate system (GCS) to define exactly where the data is located on the Earth's surface. All corresponding data frames also followed the identical CRS to avoid inaccurate spatial linkage and mapping.

RESULTS

There was a total of 2110 Redbook wildfire entries and 16 ignition causes gathered from 1980 to 2019 from 36 California counties receiving CAL FIRE services.

1980 to 1989

From 1980 to 1989, there were 553 fire events spanning 12 different ignition causes: arson, campfire, debris, electrical power, equipment-use, human, lightning, miscellaneous, play with fire, railroad, smoking, and undetermined/unidentified causes. The leading cause of fires in this decade was lightning, which accounted for nearly 23% of fires and peaked in 1987 at 80 events. Arson and equipment use were also amongst the most frequent ignition causes during this period, tallying 100 and 95 fires, respectively, followed by miscellaneous at 65 and undetermined causes

at 67 fires. Fires caused by electrical power, totaling 3 events, occurred only in 1984 during this period, and though incidents caused by debris occurred annually, they only totaled 27 fires. Fires initiated by smoking, campfire and play-with-fire tallied 15, 26 and 20 fires, respectively.

1990 to 1999

From 1990 to 1999, there were 412 of fires from 13 different ignition causes: arson, campfire, debris, electrical power, equipment use, escape, human, lightning, miscellaneous, powerlines, play with fire, smoking, causes under investigation, undetermined causes, and vehicular. Arson, lightning, and equipment-caused occurrences declined from the prior decade but were nonetheless still amongst the leading causes of fires at 68, 63, and 41 events, respectively.

Undetermined sources remained consistent and accounted for 60 fires during this period, while miscellaneous causes decreased significantly to only 12 events. Fires initiated by vehicles, powerlines, and escape emerged as new ignition sources, at 23, 10, and 5 fires, respectively, though all three causes only made up a slight percentage of the total fires experienced in California in this decade. Causes under investigation arose near the latter half of the decade, particularly from 1996 to 1999 at 11 fires.

2000 to 2010

From 2000 to 2010, there were 519 fires and 14 different ignition causes: arson, campfire, debris, electrical power, equipment use, escape, human, lightning, miscellaneous, railroad, smoking, causes under investigation, undetermined causes, and vehicular. The leading cause of fires in this decade was lightning at 140 fires and peaked in 2008, when it made up 100% of all fires in that year. Undetermined (88 fires) and equipment use (84 fires) continue to be amongst the most frequent causes of fires during this period, followed by miscellaneous sources which weighed in at 46 fires and became most prominent from 2006 and after. Fires from causes under

investigation occurred most often in 2000 and 2001 at 14 fires before declining in frequency overtime. The number of vehicular-caused fires were comparable to the preceding decade, holding nearly constant at 14 events, as did the number of debris-caused fires at 17 events.

2010 to 2019

From 2010 to 2019, there were 626 fires and 12 different ignition causes: Undetermined causes made up for 204 fires during this period, and vehicle-caused fires started 42 incidents. Lightning (19 fires) and equipment use (55 fires) continue to remain common causes, as do electrical power and debris, at 50 and 13 fires respectively. Arson-related occurrences declined to 22 fires, a marked decrease from previous years, though other human-related occurrences increased, particularly in 2012, 2013, and 2019. Causes still under investigation accounted for 30 fires.

Figure 1. Causes of wildfires in California from 1980 to 2019. 16 ignition causes and 2110 total wildfire events recorded in CALFIRE during a 40-year period. Show below if the number of fires and frequency of ignition cause(s) per year.

From 2000 to 2019, lightning, equipment use, and electrical power were the three most frequent causes of wildfires in California, accounting for 159, 139, and 54 fires, respectively, and made up nearly 31% of all fires during this period.

Lightning

Of the lightning-caused wildfire events in California from 2000 to 2019, 31 occurred in northern California, primarily in the Siskiyou and Tehama counties, which recorded six and four fires, respectively, followed by the Modoc, Lassen, Humboldt, Kern, and Trinity counties, at three fires each. The Shasta, Plumas, and Mendocino counties all experienced two fires, and one fire occurred in the Lake, Colusa, and Nevada counties.

Equipment Use

Of the equipment-use-caused wildfire events in California from 2000-2019, 26 occurred in southern California, primarily in Riverside, at six fires, and Kern and San Diego, both at three

fires. San Bernardino, San Luis Obispo, and Santa Clara each experienced two fires, and Santa Cruz, Monterey, Stanislaus, Mariposa, Madera, Fresno, Kings, and Santa Barbara had one fire.

Electrical Power

Of the electrical power-caused wildfire events in California from 2000-2019, 18 occurred in northern California, primarily in Butta and Sonoma, both at 4 fires, followed by the Siskiyou, Tehama, Mendocino, Lake, Napa, Yolo, Nevada, Amador, Calaveras, and Contra Costa counties, all at one fire.

Figure 2. The distribution of lightning, equipment-use, and electrical power-caused wildfires across California counties from 2000-2019.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

California's wildfire record from 1980 to 2019 is characterized by a steady increase in fires during the first three-quarters of the 20th century, followed by a slight decline in the early 21st century, before increasing once more in the late 2000s. This early to mid-20th century trend correlated with a changing climate and significant population growth, where clearing trees, expanding agriculture and building towns were common practices to accommodate for road and home expansion throughout the state. Subsequent infrastructural and technological advancements brought more people in contact with highly flammable fuels and placed them more at-risk of fatal accidents and crime. Wildfires also arise from California's arid and hot climate, which makes it easier for fires to start and spread through dry fuel and dry lightning that results from the fast evaporation of atmospheric and vapor moisture (Dong et al., 2022). When coupled with warmer temperatures and low precipitation- typical characteristics of climate change in states such as California- flammable fuel and lightning become major drivers of wildfires.

Of human-induced wildfires, arson had long been a major driver of intentional human ignitions on Cal Fire lands, where ignitions remained a regular occurrence during the 20th century and then dropped markedly in recent decades. As such practices and behaviors became less socially (and legally) acceptable, and soon accompanied by stricter state and federal laws regarding fire-safety, crime, and offense, arson has shown marked decline since 1996 in frequency (Keeley and Syphard, 2018). Amongst other anthropogenic causes, smoking, play-with-fire, and campfires make up only a small percentage of wildfire disasters but had a regular presence nearly every year during this 40-year study period, suggesting that communities in California most impacted by these ignition sources would benefit from increased fire-prevention management, communication, and education.

In the present study, electrical power was reported as ignition sources since the early 1980s but has become steadily more prominent in recent decades. Powerline fires, the most common form of electrical power-induced disasters, are especially widespread and dangerous because they usually occur during high winds, when the fires are capable of rapidly spreading over long distances. The 2018 Camp Fire in northern California's Butte County was one of the state's most devastating disasters, and holds the title for one of the worse wildfires on national record; it was ignited by a faulty transmission line and spurred by an east wind, which drove the fire through developed areas and communities (CALFIRE, 2023). Widespread and often inevitable reliance on electricity and power grids, however, suggests that the threat of electrical power as an ignition cause remains a pressing concern. This could call for more research and regulations when designing or stationing these powerlines, such as considering the optimal distance the structures should be spaced apart from nearby foliage and homes, or the material they are made of.

It is also noteworthy that changes in the number of ignitions for lightning-ignited fires have been one of the most dramatic of the study's 16 identified causes. Lightning accounted for most fires during the study period and is a dominant ignition source, peaking in 1987 and 2008 when California experienced a series of extreme, dry-lightning strikes in both years that amassed into two of the largest, longest-lasting wildfires (Dong et al., 2022). The number of lightning ignitions were also substantially more frequent than the leading anthropogenic causes, and more than double in the northern California counties than in the south, likely because those located at higher elevations receive more dry lightning compared to those at lower elevations (Dennison et al., 2014). It is expected that for regions with the largest increases in fire activity, temperatures were typically hotter, and precipitation lower relative to regions not experiencing significant

changes in fire activity, but lightning-strikes can also be ignited by high moisture content in the atmosphere due to high humidity and wetter conditions (Chen and Jin, 2022). In such cases, it boosts the chances of storms and extreme lightning events, which helps explain the significant increase of lightning-induced fires since the 1980s. These trends may also suggest that the recently increased large fires in California are linked to weather/climate, characterized by a longer fire season and increased wildfire activity. As extreme weather conditions continue to grow stronger and more common, they can exacerbate the occurrences of large wildfires.

In addition, because of migration patterns and distribution, populations in less fire-prone parts of the US were thus relatively naïve about the dangers of fire use in wildland areas. With fire-prevention education in its infancy in the 20th century, as were recovery systems and procedures, the population was slow to recognize their role in California's fire problem (Keeley and Syphard, 2018). Even traditional practices such as prescribed burning- which California was a pioneer in for the economic incentive of increasing rangeland- would lead to unprecedented consequences as dead biomass would act as flammable fuel for when fires do arise. Furthermore, considerable areas of wildland vegetation have been developed and fragmented in California over the course of the 20th century, and the development of such regions have surely affected ignition trends and area burned as both population and development continued to expand (Eisenman et al., 2022) (Rosenthal et al., 2021).

Undetermined causes and causes under investigation comprise a considerable number of wildfires starting from the early 1990s, likely due to modifications in CALFIRE record-keeping and categorization of ignition causes. Further research into investigating these changes in classification of causes and clarifying what is defined by 'undetermined causes' or 'causes under investigation' would be beneficial in bringing about a stronger holistic view of ignition patterns

and their significance in California. This study was also limited to just northern and southern California; region and county-specific analyses of ignition causes and trends would provide a deeper understanding of which and how particular communities are more vulnerable and/or most heavily impacted by wildfires. With these considerations and efforts, it aids in helping mitigate future disasters by improving fire-prevention strategies, recovery management, and public awareness and education.

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